

Individualizing goal-setting interventions using automated writing evaluation to support secondary school students' text revisions

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ABSTRACT

Background: Revising is central in the process of writing and for acquiring writing skills. Setting revision goals is challenging especially for novice writers: students do not revise frequently, especially in homework conditions that demand high levels of self-regulation. Empirical studies of goal-setting interventions providing a detailed list of goals show positive effects on students' revisions, and researchers have argued that individualizing such goal-setting interventions could increase intervention effectiveness.

Aims: The present study investigated an individualized goal-setting intervention that provided a list of goals based on students' previous writing using automated writing evaluation.

Sample: Participants were 345 academic track students from upper-secondary schools in Germany.

Methods: We asked students to write a text in English as a second language (ESL) as homework and then to revise it. In a hierarchical sequence of four groups, we expanded the information to support students in self-evaluating their texts and setting appropriately challenging revising goals in a stepwise manner. Students received a textbook passage showing a list of process goals (all groups), an assessment rubric (groups two, three, and four), an automated performance score (groups three and four), and individualized goal-setting instruction based on their performance score and the textbook passage (group four).

Results: Students receiving individualized goal-setting instructions showed the largest revision performance compared to the other groups, with and without controlling for text length.

Conclusions: We discuss how goal-setting support in ESL writing can benefit from automated writing evaluation to provide individualized support and thus improve the effectiveness of goal-setting interventions in supporting students' revision performances.

1. Introduction

Writing is a fundamental skill required to enable individuals to participate in society (UNESCO, 2011) and succeed in all school subjects (Graham et al., 2020). In a globalized world, writing skills in English as a second language (ESL) impact student development because the ability to write in English forms the basis for academic and business success (Keller et al., 2020). Text revisions are a central component of writing and the development of writing skills (Bereiter & Scardamalia, 1987). Revisions are defined as a problem-solving process activated by the

identification of discrepancies between the written and the intended text (Fitzgerald & Markham, 1987). Despite the importance of revisions, students in secondary school who are still novice writers do not revise frequently (Graham & Harris, 2006), extensively, or skillfully (Fitzgerald, 1987). The main reason is the complexity of those revision processes and thus, the increased need for self-regulation (Graham et al., 2017). Hence, there is a need for interventions to support students during text revision, especially during self-regulated learning phases, for example, in homework contexts. However, only eight percent of studies on writing interventions in secondary schools investigate revision performances

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(Graham et al., 2023).

Goal-setting, which involves students choosing a goal that is specific and appropriately challenging (Schunk, 1990), is a central part of the writing process (Bereiter & Scardamalia, 1987). Interventions focusing on supporting students' goal-setting presented students with a list of goals (e.g., Ferretti et al., 2009; Graham et al., 1995; Graham et al., 2021; Page-Voth & Graham, 1999; Schunk, 2003; Schunk & Schwartz, 1993; Zimmerman & Kitsantas, 1999). Meta-analyses showed that such interventions can effectively foster secondary students' writing (Graham et al., 2023; Graham & Perin, 2007). However, studies provided students with little support to apply the goals to their texts, which might limit the interventions' effectiveness. Students needed to self-evaluate their texts, compare them to the goals, and set appropriately challenging goals for their revisions. Hence, aiming to raise the effectiveness of goal-setting interventions, Graham et al. (2021) encouraged researchers to develop and test interventions based on individualized goals designed to address specific weaknesses in students' writing. Such individualized goals could be more effective because they specifically target text areas needing revision. This idea was taken up in an empirical study by Wilson et al. (2023), who presented students with individualized goals using automated writing evaluation (AWE). While this study indicated the feasibility of the approach, the study did not include a control group investigating the effectiveness of the individualized goals compared to providing general goals or other established goal-setting interventions.

This paper presents an experimental study comparing an individualized goal-setting intervention with established goal-setting interventions in the ESL homework context. All students were asked to write a text and revise their draft using a list of goals. In our experimental variation, four groups of students were provided with increasingly more detailed and individualized support to set revising goals that fit their individual level of writing. Thus, the study adds to the literature on goal setting to support students not only in setting goals but also in setting appropriately challenging goals.

1.1. Revising texts

Revisions serve a central role in several established models of writing (see Hayes, 2012; Alamargot & Chanquoy, 2001 for overviews of models). They can be described as goal-directed behaviors aiming to close the gap between the intended and the written text (Bridwell, 1980; Scardamalia & Bereiter, 1983; Sommers, 1980). Following Rijlaarsdam (2004, p. 193), revision can be defined as follows: "The (co)author or reviser reviews (part of) the already-written text, to reach a certain goal (communication goal, learning goal), at a certain text level, at a certain moment (i.e., draft, final copy), with a certain effect (i.e., improvement, neutral, weakening effect), at a certain level (text, plan, learning), and with a certain cognitive cost." Writers revise as long as their representation of their written texts reveals a dissonance between their current writing and their intended text that is important enough to warrant revision but not too difficult to prevent it from the outset (Hayes, 2004). Hence, the decision process on whether a text still needs to be revised involves several cognitive representations in the mind of the authors: a representation of the task, a representation of how the intended text should be formed, a representation of criteria for evaluating the text, and a strategy selection process about what to do after a dissonance has been detected (Hayes et al., 1987).

Revising behavior distinguishes novices from skilled writers (Bereiter & Scardamalia, 1987). Whereas skilled writers revise both their written and intended texts frequently, novices limit their revisions to their written texts and mostly to surface- and minor text-level revisions (Limpo et al., 2014; MacArthur, 2016), resulting in little or no impact on the overall quality of their text (Graham et al., 2021). Three reasons can be assumed why students do not revise: (a) an inability to set clear writing goals and intentions, which is a problem in the students' representation of their assigned writing task (their task definition, Hayes, 2004); (b) difficulties in evaluating their text from the reader's

point of view; and (c) challenges in identifying the specific areas that necessitate changes (Fitzgerald, 1987). Consequently, revisions can be initiated by changing the mental representation of the intended text or goals (Hayes, 2004), the ability to self-assess based on established evaluative criteria, and a toolbox of revising strategies alongside general language and writing skills (Fitzgerald, 1987; Flower et al., 1986).

1.2. Goal-setting for writing and revising

Goals are defined as self-proposed outcomes by the writer based on information from external and internal sources (Paris et al., 2001). Goals are critical in the writing process because they help writers understand the task at hand, consider genre conventions, structure effort, provide information on progress, and help maintain motivation and performance (Schunk, 2003). Hence, goal-setting is a central aspect of self-regulated learning in general and within writing in particular (Flower & Hayes, 1981), which is why goal-setting has a prominent position in cognitive models of writing (Hayes, 1996; Hayes & Flower, 1980). Goal-setting is also an established part of the self-regulated strategy development model (SRSD; Harris and Graham, 1992), which is the theoretical foundation for highly effective writing interventions (Graham et al., 2023). In those models, goal-setting is a central and recurring part of the writing process.

Goals are effective in the writing process if they are specific, appropriately challenging, and proximal (Harris et al., 2011; Harris & Graham, 1996). To set effective goals in an assigned writing task by a teacher, students need to possess a concept of quality (what is expected) in relation to a piece of work or task that is broadly consonant with the expected concept of the task (Sadler, 2010). Further, they need sufficient evaluative knowledge about their writing and their skills to choose appropriately challenging goals.

1.3. Goal-setting interventions

Goal-setting interventions commonly assign students with goals for writing or developing writing skills and processes (Graham et al., 2023). Such interventions are effective in supporting students writing outcomes as indicated by several meta-analyses ($ES = 2.03$ Koster et al., 2015, $ES = 0.55$ for students with learning disabilities; Gillespie & Graham, 2014; $ES = 0.44$; Graham et al., 2023). In different studies, goal-setting interventions improved different aspects of writing outcomes, like overall text quality (Graham et al., 2023), the amount of writing (Schunk & Swartz, 1993a), time spent planning and writing (Silver, 2013), and revising texts (Ferretti et al., 2000; 2009; Graham et al., 1995; Midgette et al., 2008; Page-Voth & Graham, 1999; Schunk, & Schwartz, 1993; Zimmerman & Kitsantas, 1999). The basic assumption underlying goal-setting interventions to foster revisions is that students do not revise adequately due to poorly defined goals that do not trigger a cognitive dissonance between their current writing and intended text. These interventions aim to support goal-setting by providing examples of useful goals as standards that can be reached and encourage self-assessment against these standards.

Exemplary for goal-setting interventions are the seminal series of revising studies by Schunk and Schwartz (1993a, b). They investigated the effects of showing students goals to write a descriptive paragraph and providing them with feedback in their first-language classrooms. The studies included goals focusing on the writing process (e.g., choose a topic; write down your idea; pick the main idea), showing students product goals reiterating the aim of students writing (write a descriptive paragraph), and feedback appreciating their process (e.g., you're getting good in the writing process). In their first study, fourth grade students were randomly assigned to one of three conditions over multiple weeks in their classrooms: (a) prompt to do their best, (b) process goal, or (c) process goal and feedback. Results indicated that students in the goal condition receiving feedback exhibited stronger revision performance and productivity, measured by longer paragraphs. In two subsequent

experiments with fifth-graders, students were assigned to one of four goal conditions: (a) a process learning goal, (b) a process goal plus progress feedback, (c) a product goal, or (d) a general goal (i.e., a control). In both experiments, the process goal plus feedback resulted in stronger gains in writing performance than the product and general goal.

The Interactive-Two-Feedback-Loops model (Narciss, 2008) provides a framework to describe how such goal-setting and feedback interventions might synergistically influence students' revision performances. The model highlights the importance of two intertwined feedback loops, one internal and one external. The internal loop encompasses the student understanding of the learning goals and their plan to achieve them, forming an intended text as internal reference point against which they can compare their current writing. Meanwhile, the external loop represents the assigned task standards and performance assessments working as external reference points. The model suggests that external information like assigned goals might best unfold its benefits if implemented into an interactive feedback strategy, combining external information with opportunities to generate internal feedback (e.g., by self-assessing their learning outcomes or processes). This can be achieved, for example, by asking three fundamental feedback questions: "Where am I going?", "How am I going?" and "Where to next?" (Hattie & Timperley, 2007) and providing supporting guidance for answering them (Moreno, 2004). The interplay of these loops allows for identifying a dissonance between the internal and external standards, prompting the students to take action to reconcile the two.

Empirical studies adopting the approach of showing students a list of goals could replicate Schunk and Schwartz's (1993) results in first language classrooms for students with and without learning disabilities and extend them by showing that more specific subgoals tended to raise the interventions' effectivity (Ferretti et al., 2009; Graham et al., 1995, 2021; Page-Voth & Graham, 1999). The study by Midgette et al. (2008, p. 138) is an example of such a goal-setting study, asking upper primary students to revise their essays using a list of eight goals, including "(a) make sure that your opinion is clearly stated in your essay; (b) include three or more reasons to support your main position; (c) think whether your reasons are clearly supported with examples or evidence".

1.4. Individualizing goal-setting interventions

Even when providing students with fine-grained subgoals, it can be difficult for them to assess which of these subgoals to focus on in their revision. The reason is that such lists do not provide much guidance in finding the appropriately challenging goal for each student (Graham et al., 2021). Students still need to compare their texts to each goal on their own to set appropriate goals for their revisions, which can be challenging, especially for novice writers (Graham & Harris, 2006).

Providing students with individualized goals in a goal-setting intervention could especially support novice writers in their goal-setting and text revision. Individualized goal-setting instructions could help students find the areas in which they had an incorrect representation of the task; that is, they could benefit from additional support in assessing where their definition of the writing task is not accurate to the assigned task. Individualized goal-setting instruction could also support students' self-evaluations in the parts of the texts that need improvement and provide solutions for those areas, which could raise the likelihood of implementing the set goals (Wu & Schumm, 2020). One way of providing students with individualized goal-setting instructions while taking into account their previous writing performance is using automated writing evaluation (AWE). AWE can help students determine text quality and provide them with specific goal-setting instructions according to the automated assessment.

1.5. Using automated writing evaluation to provide individualized goal-setting interventions in the writing domain

Bennett and Zhang (2015) define AWE as the automated assessment of students' answers that cannot simply be compared to a correct answer because the specific forms and content of the correct answer are not known in advance. The assessment of AWE systems is based on corpora of essays that have been hand-scored by trained raters for specific elements related to writing, for example, holistic scores of writing quality (Shermis, 2014) or argumentative elements (Crossley et al., 2022). These unstructured so-called training data, consisting of texts and human scores, are then analyzed with machine learning algorithms, which can recognize patterns in the training data and evaluate new texts on the same task based on these patterns (see Ercikan & McCaffrey, 2022, for a description of the strengths and weaknesses of the process). After careful training, AWE can predict scores by trained humans accurately and is therefore widely used in postsecondary admissions (e.g., Test of English as a Foreign Language iBT, Pearson Test of English), K-12 state assessment (e.g., Utah Direct Writing Assessment), and learning systems (see Fleckenstein et al., 2023 for a review). Comparisons between expert judgments and AWE scores showed agreements between $r = 0.60$ and $r = 0.85$, with exact agreements ranging from 30 to 60 % (Attali & Burstein, 2006; Meyer et al., 2023; Rupp et al., 2019; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). To within one level (adjacent agreement), values agreed in 85-100% (Attali & Burstein, 2006; Rupp et al., 2019; Shermis et al., 2010; Warschauer & Ware, 2006).

In current writing research, there is a strong interest in studies on AWE, as evidenced by a plethora of recent meta-analyses on the topic (Lv et al., 2021; Mohsen, 2022; Ngo et al., 2022; Zhai & Ma, 2022). Previous research has primarily used AWE to provide students with an external evaluation of their writing, that is, grading of text products (e.g., Moore & MacArthur, 2016; Roscoe & McNamara, 2013, 2019; Roscoe et al., 2014; Wade-Stein & Kintsch, 2004; Wilson, 2017; Wilson & Andrada, 2016).

It has been proposed in the literature that AWE can be useful to individualize goal-setting interventions to enhance their effectiveness (Graham et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2023), as individualized instructions allow students to focus on the specific weaknesses of their own writing. Wilson et al. (2023) first provided evidence on the effectiveness of such an individualized approach to goal-setting interventions using AWE to provide students with individualized goal-setting support according to their writing performance. However, the study did not include a control group investigating the effectiveness of the individualized goals in comparison with a condition providing general goals or other established goal-setting interventions.

1.6. Purpose of the present study

The present study addresses the problem that students do not frequently and skillfully revise their writing in the homework context, which can be caused by difficulties in setting goals for revision (Fitzgerald, 1987). Previous revision interventions aimed at supporting students' goal-setting in the classroom by providing them with a detailed list of process goals (e.g., Midgette et al., 2008) and feedback (Schunk & Schwartz, 1993a, 1993b). Individualizing goal-setting interventions using automated writing evaluation can help students focus on the goals most important to their writing, addressing the specific potentials for improvements and weaknesses of their texts (Graham et al., 2021). Further, AWE could support the application of goal-setting interventions not only within classroom but also in context without teacher oversight like homework. So far, little empirical research has investigated the effectiveness of individualized goal-setting interventions, and the studies that did (Wilson et al., 2023) had no control group. To extend the empirical evidence on the effectiveness of individualized goal-setting interventions further, the present study compares general goal-setting support with individualized goal-setting support within four groups. In

a randomized experiment in the homework context, each setting sequentially provides more support for students to set appropriately challenging goals for their revisions in writing. We asked all students to write an ESL essay and revise it using a textbook passage showing a list of process goals. During revision, the first group received only the textbook passage (control group). The second group additionally received an assessment rubric to prompt self-evaluation regarding the list of goals. The third group additionally received a performance score to support the self-evaluation of the texts regarding the goals with external feedback. The fourth group additionally received an individualized goal-setting intervention by receiving individualized goals through specific highlighting from the textbook passage. The first three groups were designed following established goal-setting interventions in previous research (Schunk & Schwartz, 1993a). The fourth group expanded the established set-up by providing individualized goals that focused on one area of improvement. We hypothesized that presenting students with individualized goals in the fourth group would enhance their revision performance and productivity compared to the other three groups. We also conducted robustness checks investigating whether the effects of the different groups would relate to students' English marks.

2. Method

2.1. Transparency and openness

We report how we determined our sample size, all data exclusions, all manipulations, and all measures in the study. We followed the Journal Article Reporting Standards (JARS, Kazak, 2018). All data, analysis codes, and research materials are available at <https://osf.io/6r3es/>. The analysis was carried out using R (version 4.1.0; R Core Team, 2020). The study's design and its analysis were not preregistered. The Ethics and Data Protection Commission of the Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education (IPN) reviewed the study.

2.2. Sample

Participants were $N = 345$ academic track students from upper-secondary schools in Germany; this level corresponds to Level 3 according to the International Standard Classification of Education. The sample came from 21 schools that participated in the study as homework. After finishing, students' homework was automatically sent to the class teacher. The mean age was 16.82 years ($SD = 1.46$). In the sample, 59% reported their gender as female, 37% as male, 2% as non-binary, and 2% refused to indicate their gender. Participants received, on average, 9.57 ($SD = 3.58$) points in English in their last school year on a scale from zero to 15. More points represent higher achievement. Participants did not receive any incentives to participate. Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous. The sample was randomly within classes assigned to four groups ($n = 76/96/80/93$). We did not exclude any participants from the dataset. Based on the written texts and the time stamp in the data, we did not identify outliers that wrote texts that did not match the task or did answer the questions unrealistically fast. Thus, we included all participants in the analyses. We had no missing values because responding to all questions was mandatory in the online system.

2.3. Automated scoring algorithm

We trained a machine learning algorithm to score students' writing based on training data from a similar learning context (Keller et al., 2020). The aim was to align our scoring criteria with our specific curriculum, and thus also align writing goals to students' writing competence. This approach allowed us to tailor individualized goals more closely to students' needs, as opposed to using general models trained on data from other populations (see Crossley et al., 2022 for training data from other populations). Our training data included texts from 2420

students written to the same prompt used in the present study (58.1% female, mean age = 17.7 years). Rigorously trained expert raters scored each text on a holistic scale (see Supplementary Material, Figure S1) from zero (low quality) to five (high quality). The prompt and rating scale was developed for the TOEFL (Rupp et al., 2019). The text corpus is described in detail in Keller et al. (2020); the rater training, and the rating process in Rupp et al. (2019). The experts reached a high exact agreement on 62.5% of the texts and showed a quadratic weighted kappa of .67. When the experts did not agree on a text, a third expert with several years of experience as a master rater decided on the final score.

We used the final score to train the scoring algorithm using a support vector machine (Pedregosa et al., 2011), which is, in the broadest sense, linear regression in more than two dimensions. It is similar to linear regression in that the algorithm optimizes a prediction to have the minimum distance to the data points. The main difference is that support vector machines use a higher dimensional surface, a so-called hyperplane, instead of a line. To train the support vector machine, we first evaluated over one hundred linguistic features to use them as predictors. The features included lexical information (word n-grams), structural information (part-of-speech n-grams), text length, and complexity features. Second, we identified the most relevant features to classify the texts into six categories based on the human scores. Third, we built the optimal hyperplane that separates the data points into six scores by minimizing the margin between the hyperplane and the closest data points. Fourth, we classified new texts using the hyperplane. The scoring algorithm was implemented in a Java-based toolbox for free-text scoring based on natural language processing and machine learning (Horbach et al., 2017; Zesch & Horbach, 2018). In a cross-validation setup on the training data, the algorithm reached an exact agreement with the human ratings on 43.9% of the texts and showed a quadratic weighted kappa of .76 between human and expert ratings.

2.4. Predictor variable: Goal-setting intervention

We divided participants into four experimental groups, where the first three goal-setting interventions resembled those in previous research, and the fourth introduced individualized goals to enhance the intervention's effectiveness. The setting in each group sequentially added more support for students to self-evaluate their texts and set appropriately challenging revising goals. In group one, all students were shown a textbook passage to prompt their self-evaluation (control group). The text-book passage provided a frame of reference for their revision by showing them a list of subgoals for three steps of the writing process, namely planning, writing, and proofreading (see for similar goal-setting operationalizations Ferretti et al., 2009; Page-Voth & Graham, 1999). The textbook passage was chosen based on students' curricula and included information on planning, writing, and proofreading according to Hayes and Flower's (1980) writing model.

Group 2 (rubric) extended the general goals by providing an assessment rubric that included more detailed information for students' self-evaluation (see for a similar goal-setting operationalization Ferretti et al., 2000). The top box in Fig. 1 and supplementary Figure S3 show the operationalization of the assessment criteria. We chose this operationalization because it corresponds to the highest level of the holistic TOEFL scale we used to assess the texts and create the scoring algorithm (see Figure S1). Further, these established criteria have been shown to correspond to the school curricula within the tested region (Fleckenstein et al., 2020a) and are similar to the criteria teachers use in the classroom (Llosa & Malone, 2017).

Group 3 (performance score) extended the rubric group by including a holistic performance score on a scale from 0 to 5 (see middle box in Fig. 1 and supplementary Figure S4), reflecting students' draft performance to show whether the students have room for improvement in their writing (see for other studies combining goal-setting with performance feedback Schunk & Schwartz, 1993a; Torrance et al., 2015;

As feedback on your first text, we have provided additional information on this page. Use the information to revise your text.

Where am I going?

Try to write a text that accomplishes all of the following points.

The text...

- *effectively addresses the topic and task.
- * is well organized and well developed, using clearly appropriate explanations, exemplifications and/or details.
- *displays unity, progression and coherence.
- *displays consistent facility in the use of language, demonstrating syntactic variety, appropriate word choice and idiomaticity, though it may have minor lexical or grammatical errors.

How is it going?

Your text reached the Score: 2.0. The maximum score is 5.

Your score corresponds to the Level B1 - intermediate for productive writing performance on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages.

Where to next?

Concentrate on the following checkpoints. These were selected for you from the checklist below based on your score.

Writing		
Introduction	Main Part	Conclusion
<p>You present the issue. To attract the reader's attention, you can include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ facts about the history/background of the topic, ✓ information about their relevance today, ✓ a quote or questions to which you provide answers. <p>You can also give your point of view here.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ State, demonstrate and describe positive and negative effects of the topic ✓ Support your view of the situation by giving examples. You can refer quote experts on this matter or relate your view to other comparable issues. ✓ Emphasize the argument by referring to further/future consequences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Conclude your comment by giving your personal view of the issue. ✓ Try to relate your final remarks to your introduction in order to 'wrap up' the topic and make your point, but do not use the exact same phrases as in the introduction. ✓ Do not give new information.

Fig. 1. Example feedback for students with a draft of medium quality in the individualized goal-setting group.

Note: Students in the individualized goals group saw all three boxes. Students in the performance score group saw the upper two boxes. Students in the rubric group saw only the upper box, and students in the control group saw none of these boxes. Students in all groups saw the textbook material displayed in Figure S2.

Wilson et al., 2023). Prior work shows that less than 5% of the students from the population reach the highest level (Rupp et al., 2019); hence, we assumed that for the great majority of students, the score would indicate that there is still a gap between the current and the target performance.

Group 4 (individualized goals) extended the performance score with an individualized goal statement to focus on some checkpoints in the textbook passage. Students who submitted a low-quality draft (score: 0–1) saw the highlighted textbook passage on how to plan their writing by first collecting the pros and cons for each opinion, then sorting their arguments logically, and finally, forming their own opinion. Students who submitted a medium-quality draft (score: 2–3) saw the highlighted textbook passage on how to improve the introduction, body, and conclusion. Students who submitted a high-quality draft (score: 4–5) saw the highlighted textbook passage on proofreading. The assignment of scores to the excerpts of the textbook material emerged from discussions with experts in second-language writing, who were familiar with the scoring of the training data set and the distribution of students' problems in the text. In the discussions, we read texts at each level and discussed what specific subgoal they should work on next. Compared to the other groups, the setting in the individualized goals group provided students with instructions on which specific part of the general textbook material was relevant to them at the current level of their writing performance. The different versions of the goal-setting interventions (together with example texts within the different groups) are shown in Figure S5 in the supplementary material.

2.5. Outcome variables: writing performance and productivity

Students' writing performance was estimated based on the scoring algorithm described above, which was used to rate both the draft and the revised text on a holistic six-point scale ranging from zero to five. The rubric is similar to the one used in the TOEFL test of independent writing (Rupp et al., 2019). The number of characters, including spaces, in students' drafts and revised text indicated the text length and was taken as a proxy of students' productivity (see Wilson & Andrade, 2016, for an overview of studies using similar operationalizations).

2.6. Procedure

The study was conducted in a four-group between-subject design. Students were randomly assigned to the four groups. The study was conducted with an online tool based on the platform *LimeSurvey*, which showed the students a sequence of web pages. On average, students took 49 min to complete the study. The procedure is shown in Fig. 2.

Participants wrote their draft in 20 min to the writing prompt: "Do you agree or disagree with the following statement? A teacher's ability to relate well with students is more important than excellent knowledge of the subject being taught." They saw the prompt and received the information that a text that fulfills the assessment criteria should be about 300 words long. After they finished the draft, the text was automatically scored within 5 seconds. Next, participants had another 20 min to revise their text using the textbook material, rubric, performance score, or

Fig. 2. Study procedure.

individualized goals. After completing the revision, participants' demographic information was collected on the last page.

2.7. Statistical analyses

We tested the differences between the four groups in multilevel models. In all three models, we used time point (0 – draft; 1 – revision) as a repeated factor. To indicate differences between groups, we used three dummy variables, one for the control group (control), the rubric group (rubric), and the performance score group (score) group as between factors. The individualized goals group functioned as the reference category. In Model 1, we included the factors time, group, and the time*group interaction to test if participants revised their writing differently in the groups. In the first robustness check, we added students' marks and text length as covariates (Model 2). We standardized the covariates per cluster, meaning that covariates were standardized by the mean and standard deviation of the corresponding group. We conducted this check to investigate whether we find the differences in improvement between groups, controlling for the differences in text length or students' marks between participants. In a second robustness check, we added the three-way interaction between the time point, the groups, and the students' marks to test whether the feedback effect differs for students depending on their prior marks in English classes (Model 3). The analysis code can be found at <https://osf.io/6r3es/>. We calculated the models once for the writing performance and once for

productivity as the outcome variable.

3. Results

The descriptive results for the writing performance in the draft and the revision are shown in Table 1, together with the sample characteristics. The four groups did not differ in the composition of age, mark for English, gender, and writing performance before the revision, suggesting successful randomization (all $F [3, 341] < 1.00, p > .394$; see Table 1 for the descriptive results for each group).

Across groups, the mean score was $M = 2.93$ ($SD = 0.78$) points in the draft and $M = 3.40$ ($SD = 0.75$) points in the revision, representing a mean revision effect of $d = 0.62$. Participants in the control group improved their texts by revising with the textbook material, on average, by 0.38 ($SD = 0.61$) points on the holistic scale. Their draft and revision scores correlated with $r = 0.65$. The high correlation indicates that the scores remained rather stable after the revision. The average improvement in the rubric group was 0.43 ($SD = 0.68$), with a correlation between draft and revision scores of $r = 0.59$. The score group improved on average 0.43 ($SD = 0.68$) points, with a correlation between draft and revision scores of $r = 0.75$. Finally, the individualized goals group improved on average 0.66 ($SD = 0.87$) points and had the lowest draft with revision score correlation of $r = 0.37$.

Results for the writing performance as the outcome measure (see Table 2, Model 1) showed a significant positive main effect of time,

Table 1
Means (Standard Deviations) Split by the Feedback Groups.

Feedback	Draft score (0–5)	Revision score (0–5)	Age in years	% Female	English mark (0–15)	No. char. draft	No. char. revision
Control	2.97 (0.77)	3.36 (0.69)	16.70 (2.17)	64 (.48)	9.47 (3.85)	1336 (555)	1806 (611)
Rubric	2.92 (0.75)	3.35 (0.75)	16.76 (1.15)	54 (.50)	9.85 (3.58)	1269 (458)	1736 (565)
Score	2.86 (0.79)	3.25 (0.80)	16.81 (1.29)	63 (.49)	8.97 (3.61)	1259 (556)	1647 (603)
Individualized goals	2.96 (0.83)	3.61 (0.69)	16.98 (1.13)	58 (.50)	9.85 (3.33)	1361 (507)	1857 (549)

Note. No. char = number of characters to measure text length.

Table 2
Results of Multilevel Models Predicting Scores of Texts as Outcome Variable in Comparison to the Individualized goals group as Reference Category.

	Model 0		Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	Est.	<i>p</i>	Est.	<i>P</i>	Est.	<i>p</i>	Est.	<i>p</i>
fixed effects								
intercept	0.28	<.001	2.96	<.001	2.89	<.001	2.91	<.001
time			0.65	<.001	0.62	<.001	0.61	<.001
control			0.02	.886	0.02	.854	0.01	.918
rubric			−0.04	.714	0.03	.691	0.03	.735
score			−0.09	.413	0.02	.830	0.03	.735
time*control			−0.27	.011	−0.23	.021	−0.22	.027
time*rubric			−0.22	.031	−0.18	.051	−0.18	.058
time*score			−0.27	.012	−0.20	.048	−0.19	.055
time*mark							0.10	.163
length					0.48	<.001	0.47	<.001
mark					0.10	<.001	0.00	.987
mark*control							0.09	.331
mark*rubric							0.06	.531
mark*score							0.21	.020
time*mark*control							−0.09	.328
time*mark*rubric							−0.07	.487
time*mark*score							−0.11	.292
random effects								
$\hat{\tau}_{00}$.28		.33		.13		.13	
$\hat{\sigma}^2$.36		.24		.19		.18	
$R^2_{\text{Level 1}}$.33		.47		.50	
$R^2_{\text{Level 2}}$			−.18		.54		.54	

Note. R^2 are calculated compared to Model 0; time differs between 0 (draft) and 1 (revision); τ indicates the Level 2 variance, σ indicates the Level 1 variance; control, rubric, and score are dummy variables indicating participants' group; length indicates text length operationalized as number of characters; mark indicates students mark in English in the last year; Model 1 test differences in improvement from draft and revision between groups; Model 2 integrates the covariates and Model 3 the interactions between groups and covariates.

indicating that writing performances were higher in the revision than in the draft. Comparing the improvement between groups, we found significant interactions between the time point and the three dummy variables. The negative estimates indicate that the largest improvements in students' writing performance took place in the reference category, i.e., the individualized goal group, compared to the control, rubric, and score group.

In Model 2, we added learners' school marks and text length as covariates. The main effects for the covariates showed positive estimates, indicating that longer texts had a higher quality and students who received more points in their last English exam showed a higher writing performance. Further, Model 2 showed similar results as Model 1 for our central result that the individualized goal group improved their writing quality more than the other groups. Hence, differences in marks and text length between groups cannot explain the differences in writing performance between groups. In Model 3, we added a three-way interaction between mark, time, and group into the model to test if the model interventions effects differ between students according to their marks. The pattern for the interaction effects between time and groups remained the same even under control of the three way interaction, indicating that in this model as well the individualized goal group improved their texts more strongly in the revision. In sum, our results showed that improvements of students in the individualized goals group exceeded those of students in the rubric group (0.18) and in the control and score group (0.27) on the 0–5 metric (see Table 1). Notably, we found a positive estimate for the interaction between the mark and score group. This suggests that students with higher marks in the score group achieved higher writing performances in draft and revision.

We calculated two corresponding models with productivity (i.e., text length) instead of writing performance as the outcome variable. In Model 1, we included the variables time, group, and the interaction between time and group. In Model 2, we added mark and the three-way interaction between group, time, and mark as covariates. Results showed a significant positive effect of time, indicating that after the revision, texts were longer than in the draft (see Table S1). Comparing the productivity between groups, we found no significant interactions between time points and the three dummy variables in Model 1 or Model 2. Thus, we did not find differential increases in text length between the

groups. In Model 2, we found a significant positive interaction between time and mark, indicating that students with higher marks added more words to their drafts in the revision. Further, we found a positive estimate for the interaction between mark and score group. The result suggests that students with better marks in the score group wrote longer texts in the draft and revision. This result does not suggest that students with better marks profited more from the score because we did not find a significant three-way interaction between mark, time, and the score group.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to investigate if providing students with individualized goals based on their own writing performance can enhance the effectiveness of goal-setting interventions. We assumed individualized goals would support students in their text revision by helping them focus on the specific aspects of their writing that needed revision to improve the quality of their writing. We hypothesized that such individualized goal-setting interventions would help students set appropriately challenging goals for their revision compared to more generic goal-setting interventions. To individualize the goals, we used automated writing evaluations to combine the potential of automated assessments with goal-setting interventions described in (foreign language) writing research (Graham et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2023).

The results showed that students within the individualized goal-setting group outperformed students in the other groups regarding improving their texts in the revision. The result remained stable when including mark, text length and their interactions as control variables, which means that differences in students' marks and text lengths could not explain the shown group difference. We interpret the findings as support for the idea that effective goals need to be appropriately challenging, and that the effectiveness of goal-setting interventions can be enhanced by providing students with individualized goal-setting instructions aligned with their prior writing performance (Graham et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2023). One plausible interpretation of our findings aligns closely with the principles of the two-way feedback loop model (Narciss, 2008). In this model, the individualized textbook passage, performance scores, and rubrics may have instigated a dissonance

within the students' internal feedback loops. This cognitive dissonance could encourage students to reevaluate and recalibrate their self-set goals. The individualization of goals built on automated writing evaluations may, in turn, have made these external cues more effective in assisting students in reconciling this dissonance given their writing, thus setting more appropriately challenging goals. An alternative explanation for our results would be that students in the individualized goal-setting groups had more time to work on the revisions compared with students who first had to determine which of the possible revisions they should focus on by themselves. Without individualized support, students first have to choose which goal they want to prioritize in their revision, whereas this choice was easier for students in the individualized goal-setting group. This means the groups differ not only in how the goal-setting intervention was provided but also in the time available to students to work on their revisions. According to [Duijnhouwer et al. \(2012\)](#), the availability of time for reflection can significantly impact the effectiveness of instruction: students who receive individualized goals likely set their revision goals more quickly than those in other groups. Doing so would give them more time to engage deeply in the revision process.

In contrast to our hypotheses and previous studies (e.g., [Graham et al., 1995](#)), we found no differences between the groups regarding students' productivity in the revision. This means that, although students improved in the revision regarding quality criteria based on the result of the interventions, students in the individualized goals group did not write longer texts. The result contributes to the discussion about the relation of text length and quality in students' second language texts (see [Fleckenstein et al., 2020b](#)) and indicates that the individualized goals triggered revision processes that go beyond merely writing longer texts during revision: students' texts became better, though not necessarily longer. We could take our results to mean that students receiving individualized goals might be setting more appropriately challenging goals for revision, which allowed them to focus on the most important weaknesses of their writing.

Further, we observed that students receiving a performance score or using a rubric, which should support self-evaluation, did not exhibit any improvement through revising in writing performance or productivity compared to the textbook group. These results stand in contrast with previous findings in the context of primary students ([Schunk & Schwartz, 1993a,b](#); [Zimmerman & Kitsantas, 1999](#)). One possible explanation for this discrepancy is that our sample consisted of secondary students who may already possess more self-evaluation skills, diminishing the added value of the information that the texts could be improved in a revision. Besides, the students may already have been familiar with the assessment criteria because the rubric we used, derived from the TOEFL test, aligns closely with their school curriculum goals for writing ([Fleckenstein et al., 2020a](#)).

4.1. Limitations

When interpreting our results, several limitations need to be considered. First, the accuracy of the automated writing evaluation should be taken into account. Automated writing evaluation can assess writing performances as accurately as trained humans and has established itself in postsecondary admissions. The performance of our scoring algorithm was comparably close to that of these established algorithms and human ratings ([Meyer et al., 2023](#); [Rupp et al., 2019](#); [Shermis et al., 2010](#); [Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019](#)), but the performance was still far from perfect. As our individualized goals and our outcome variable were both based on the scoring algorithm, erroneous scorings would have doubly biased the results. Incorrect scores add noise to the data because evaluations that are too negative could demotivate students ([Fong et al., 2019](#)), whereas scores that are too positive could be perceived as praise by students, and this might raise their performance ([Wisniewski et al., 2020](#), but cf. [Lipnevich et al., 2023](#)). It is important to note that although inaccurate scoring is a serious problem, it is not

specific to automated scoring. It is also challenging for teachers to assess student performance accurately ([Südkamp et al., 2012](#)), especially in the writing domain (e.g., [Jansen et al., 2021](#), [Möller et al., 2022](#)). Being aware of the extent of the unreliability of automated feedback is a strength of the approach. Further, our automated assessment provided only a general, holistic score as a measure for improvement. Revision effectiveness could be studied in more detail by taking different aspects of text quality into account in an analytic rating ([Wu & Schunn, 2020](#)).

Second, while our study provides valuable insights into the role of individualized goals in improving goal-setting interventions, it also raises important questions for future research. Our operationalization of individualized goals always included a performance score. As we did not include an individualized goals group without a performance score, we cannot say if the individualized goals are more effective because they combine all information or solely because they presented individualized goal-setting instructions alone. This question remains an avenue for further research.

Third, the effects of the textbook passages and rubrics are dependent on students' understanding of the goals ([Wu & Schunn, 2020](#)). We assumed that students received the necessary instruction to understand the material because the goals formulated in the assessment criteria aligned with their curriculum ([Fleckenstein et al., 2020a](#)). Notably, the approach to providing a goal-setting intervention without additional instruction differs from the goal-setting literature, which often combines goal-setting with multiple-week-long courses (e.g., [Graham et al., 1995](#)). In the present study, we designed the writing environment to contain nothing but the needed information to avoid confounding effects of the intervention. Accordingly, our results apply to this type of goal-setting intervention, and it remains unclear whether the pattern of results would hold for different operationalization of goals within other instructional components.

Fourth, we would like to point out that because of our scoring approach, our individualized goals varied only within three steps, which did not fully use the potential of individualization. A more detailed individualization of the goals could further enhance the effectiveness of the interventions, for example, by highlighting specific information in the textbook or ordering the goals for the students. Accordingly, the individualized goal-setting intervention based on automated writing evaluation might have been more effective if we had operationalized it with more details on text qualities like content, structure, or style instead of just an assessment of holistic text quality.

Fifth, it is important to note that the observed differences between groups solely pertain to revision performance, not necessarily to the acquisition of writing and revision competencies. One could argue that students who received less support in goal-setting, although their revision improvements might lag, may expend more effort in goal-setting than those receiving more support. This effort could cause greater learning gains for the next writing task. Future studies are needed to test this hypothesis. The limitation underscores the need for further research in this area and necessitates evaluating the effectiveness of individualized goal-setting across various learning measures and revision performance.

On a sixth and final note, we found that students in the score group who reported having higher marks in English achieved higher scores and wrote longer texts in the draft and the revision than students reporting low marks in English. The effect may indicate a problem with the random assignment of participants to groups rather than a intervention effect because we could not find a three-way interaction between time, mark, and score groups. However, with respect to the three-way interaction, it is important to emphasize that our sample was too small to detect such detailed interaction effects with sufficient power.

4.2. Implications for research and practice

By leveraging technology, researchers can experiment with individualizations on a larger scale, enhancing the speed and efficiency of

their studies. The efficacy of individualized goals found in this study serves as a starting point, aiming to improve the effectivity of established writing interventions with individualization. Such individualization, extended for multiple writing prompts and contexts, holds great potential to supplement writing classrooms. Future studies should, on the one hand, investigate more fine-grained individualizations than this study and, on the other hand, explore the potential of task general machine learning models for this task to raise the applicability of individualized goal-setting interventions.

For school practice, the study suggests that teachers might benefit from automated writing evaluation technologies to support students individually. However, we would like to note that to build individualized writing instructions in the classroom, more research is needed on evaluation that can be delivered automatically but still capture more nuanced aspects of writing in order to individualize the goals. Still, our study provides some evidence that individualized goals can be conducive to revision performance in the writing domain, even when the individualized goal-setting intervention is based on a rather general AWE algorithm.

Another implication of our study is that goal-setting interventions can work within homework conditions without requiring teacher oversight. The result adds to the literature because previous studies used goal-setting interventions only in the classroom and mostly over extended periods of time. Our findings suggest a potential scalability of these interventions extending beyond the classroom environment, allowing students to engage in revisions without adding to teachers' workload.

5. Conclusion

In summary, we view the contribution of our study as twofold: First, we found empirical support for the idea that effective goals need to be appropriately challenging and thus, the individualization of goals to students writing can increase the effectiveness of goal-setting interventions for text revision in the context of homework. Working in this context places a high demand of self-regulation on students, thus producing a particular need for effective interventions supporting students not only in setting goals but setting appropriately challenging goals. Second, our results indicated that automated writing evaluation can be useful to enhance the effectiveness and applicability of theory-based writing interventions. Future studies might utilize AWE within strategy-based writing instruction to individualize other types of writing intervention.

Author note

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thorben Jansen: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision. **Jennifer Meyer:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Johanna Fleckenstein:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Andrea Horbach:** Software, Writing – review & editing. **Stefan Keller:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Jens Möller:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used GPT4 in order to generate ideas and improve language. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2023.101847>.

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